

Understanding Today's Economic

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The word economic can be sometimes confusing if we are not used to the basic fundamentals that goes with it. We usually get attracted to the word “Economic” when things do not work the way we wanted it to go. Prices rises and falls, jobs are no longer available, basic needs are questionable is where we tend to ask questions what is going on. The recent global pandemic has created a new wave of uncertainty among companies and individuals.

First is First

The saying “Knowledge Is Power” is very true when one wants to understand about economic. Three categories should be comprehended, “The Past, The Present and The Future”. Only once you have got some basics ideas of what have happened in the past, then you be able to compare and see what is happening at the present. If you have understood this part and then the next step is to foresee the future that you want to build for you. Sometimes, we get clouded on what we want to have based on other person’s aims and judgement of the economic.

Therefore, First is First, understand what have really happen in the past related to economics. You can simply start by selecting an “Era” that you want to understand in the past, example in 1930 when the world order was in confusion due to war. Now, there is simple way to have this analysed in a systematic technique for building the blocks of knowledge that you need.

I came to know the PESTEL Analysis model decades back during my universities days in a project management class. While busy trying to focus on the given assignment, the history of PESTLE Analysis sparked me that is this analysis only can be used as a framework used by marketers to monitor and analyse the macro environmental for an organisation or it can also be used by an individual to see what is going on his/her life.

PESTEL Analysis for an Individual

Based on various literatures, PESTEL Analysis became very popular during the twentieth century which is widely used in project management to study environmental factors that can make or break the accomplishment of the project. The history of this model goes back to 1967 when Francis J. Aguilar [1] firstly introduced with four elements to scan the business environment known as “ETPS” to address Economic, Technical, Political and Social. After decades, it is now commonly used as PESTEL with six factors known as Political, Economic, Social, Technological, Legal and Environmental. You can simply find more definition online.

So let’s question these factors based on 1930 Era.

1. Political – How was the political situation conditions at that time?
2. Economic – What is really the financial wealth of a country or an organisation?
3. Social – What was the social situation or social obligations?
4. Technological – What kind of technology level was going on?
5. Environmental – How the environment and surroundings in 1930?
6. Legal – What were the laws?

Recap the Article

The simplified question above was constructed to allow the readers to think and see how these elements can be used by an individual to see the past or present that they want to understand before event predicting the future. To recap, the introduction of the article highlighted on the confusion of the word economic and how one can understand in a systematic technique. Therefore, I introduced PESTEL where it can be the basic of building the blocks of knowledge that you need to understand first.

Put yourself in the middle and surround it by these six factors and see what was going on. Ask questions like what I was doing in “**The Past**” when a political change was going on? What am I doing at “**The Present**” when Technology innovation is thriving? What will be “**The Future**” environment and how I see myself at that time? Ask all the questions focusing on the six factors and you will realize that economic is no longer a word of confusion.

On my next article, I will write more about how the PESTEL Analysis can be further developed with SWOT Analysis. Remember, the aim for this article is to use various models to develop your understanding on economic that are widely used in industries. The approach is to allow ourselves to use some of the models to find our directions in the uncharted era we are marching on.

Reference:

[1] F.J Aguilar, “Scanning the Business Environment,” MacMillan Co., New York, 1967